

Study of Bacteria On the Body Surfaces of House Flies (*Musca Domestica*) In Some Homes Within Sokoto Metropolis

Yalli A.A. *, Sambo S., Lawal H.M., Tukur U.

Department of Biology, Shehu Shagari College of Education, Sokoto Nigeria.

*Corresponding author: Yalli Abu Abdulkarim, Phone: +234(0)7031933442, Email: yalliabdulkarim@gmail.com

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ABSTRACT:

Housefly (*Musca domestica*), lives in close association with people all over the world. The insects feed on human foodstuffs and wastes and transmit various disease agents. They carry bacteria on their bodies from sewers, drains and garbage areas and then transmit it to individuals by visiting their kitchens. Houseflies spread a range of diseases and are a health hazard. This study was carried out to isolate and identify the bacteria on the external body surfaces of *Musca domestica* collected from toilet, Kitchen and Room in some areas within Sokoto metropolis, Nigeria. Houseflies were collected by using sticky traps or direct collection. Pathogenic bacteria were isolated from the external surfaces of the sampled examined. The study revealed high bacteria counts in all three locations, with toilets having the highest count of 3.9×10^8 cfu/ml and room with the least count of 3.4×10^5 cfu/ml. The bacteria isolated from these samples includes: *Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas* spp., *Bacillus* spp., *Enterobacter* spp., *Staphylococcus* spp., *Salmonella* spp., *Proteus* spp. and *Klebsiella* spp. Total loads of the bacterial isolates from the three sites revealed that the isolates obtained from toilets were high as compared to those from kitchen and rooms. This indicated that *Musca domestica* is a possible reservoir of several pathogens via their bodies and showed that their presence in the kitchen due to unhygienic conditions can threaten the health of the populace by causing serious illness. It is recommended that suitable steps must be taken to monitor and control the sensitivity pattern of the bacterial pathogens transmitted by the houseflies.

Keyword: Bacteria, *Musca domestica*, Body surfaces, Homes, and Diseases.

INTRODUCTION

The common housefly (*Musca domestica*), lives in close association with people all over the world, the insects feed on human foodstuffs and wastes where they can pick up and transport various disease agents. In addition to the housefly, a number of other fly species have adapted to life in human settlements, where they present similar problems [1]. In warmer climates, the houseflies are considered important in the spread of eye infections [2]. Flies can spread diseases because they feed freely on human food and filthy matter alike. The fly picks up disease-causing organisms while crawling and feeding. Those that stick to the outside surfaces of the fly may survive for only a few hours, but those that are ingested with the food may survive in the fly's crop or gut for several days [3]. Transmission takes place when the fly makes contact with people or their food. Most of the diseases can also be contracted more directly through contaminated food, water, air, hands and person-to-person contact. This reduces the relative importance of flies as carriers of disease.

In Nigeria, Adeymi and Dipeolu [4], isolated seven genera of bacteria, some of which were pathogenic to humans, were isolated from legs, wings, mouth parts and mid gut of the flies. Low numbers of bacteria were isolated from flies caught in areas where hygienic condition prevailed. *Bacillus* species were the most numerous of the bacteria isolated. The greatest numbers of bacteria were on the legs infected the house fly (*Musca domestica*) with a liquid suspension of *Campylobacter jejuni*; 20% of the bacteria were recovered from the feet and ventral surface of the body and 70% from the viscera [5]. These findings demonstrated the potential role of flies in the dissemination of avian campylobacteriosis.

Also Umeche and Mandah [6], arrived to the same observations. Cholera, the causative organism of which is *Vibrio comma*, was among the first disease in which house fly was incriminated as a vector. Though, flies have the mechanism and habits for the transmission of the tubercle bacillus, no conclusive

work have established the relationships of the flies to such transmission [2, 3]. The importance of the house fly wings in mechanical transmission of vibrio cholera was discussed [7] because of the low transfer rate of the bacteria to wings.

The main objective of this study was to isolate and identified bacteria on the external body parts of Housefly (*Musca domestica*) from kitchens, toilet and house surrounding collected from different homes within Sokoto metropolis, Nigeria.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Area

This study on isolation and identification of pathogenic microorganisms (bacteria), on the external body parts of Housefly (*Musca domestica*) from kitchens, toilet and rooms was carried out in some houses within Sokoto metropolis (Sokoto state). The State geographically lies along longitude $11^{\circ} 30'$ to $13^{\circ} 50'$ East and latitudes 4° to 6° North and covers a total land mass of 26,648.48 square kilometres. Sokoto State shares boundary with Kebbi State to the south, Zamfara State to the east and the Republic of Niger to the north. The State has an estimated population of about 4,742,459 people as of 2015 with 95.9 persons per square kilometre, and 3% growth rate annually based on 2006 population census [8]. Occupation of city inhabitants includes farming, trading, commerce, with a reasonable proportion of the population working in private and public sectors [9, 10].

Samples Analysis

Total of 150 samples were collected from kitchens, toilet and rooms to test the presence of pathogenic bacteria. All these samples were used for the culturing of microorganisms.

Sample analysis was done according to the standard plate count procedures outlined by Oyeleke and Manga [11].

Serial dilution was carried out by pipetting 1ml from the stock bottle and transferring it to another universal bottle containing 9mls of distilled water. This bottle was marked 10^1 .

Similar procedures were carried out up to 10^6 . From the bottle with dilution of 10^6 , media inoculation was done.

Media Preparation

Nutrient agar and MacConkey agar were prepared according to the manufacturers procedures.

Nutrient Agar

23g of the powder was weighed using a balance and transferred into 1000ml distilled water contained in a conical flask. Heating was done to dissolve the powder completely. This was followed by autoclaving at 121°C for 15mins. This was dispersed into the Petridishes and allowed to solidify.

Macconkey Agar

52g of the dry powder was weighed using a balance and transferred into 1000ml distilled water contained in a conical flask. Heating was done to dissolve the powder completely. This was dispersed into the petridishes and allowed to solidify.

Media Inoculation

0.1ml of the diluent from 10^6 bottle was transferred to the petridishes using a pipette. A sterilized bent glass rod (in alcohol) was used to spread the inoculum over the surface of the petridishes. The set up was incubated at 37°C for 24hrs. Plates showing no growth were further incubated for 48hrs before discarding.

Sub Culturing

The suspected colonies after gram stained were subculture on another fresh nutrient agar plate for pure culture. Confirmed purified isolates were transferred to slants for further analysis mostly biochemical reactions.

Biochemical Reactions

The following reactions were carried out; catalase, coagulase, mannitol, reactions on Triple sugar Iron Agar, spore staining temperature treatment, urease, oxidase, citrate and MRVP. The procedures were according to the method employed [11].

Catalase Test

A drop of 3% hydrogen peroxide was placed on a glass slide. A bit of growth from a solid medium was removed with a wire loop and placed in a drop of hydrogen peroxide on the glass slide. A positive test was indicated by bubbling and frothing. In a negative test no bubbling and frothing.

Coagulase Test

Two drops of physiological saline was placed about 2cm apart on a clean glass slide that has been divided into two with a grease pencil, one colony was carefully emulsified in each drop of saline. A loopful of citrated human plasma was added to the bacterial suspension on one side and was mixed with the wire loop. The slide was held up and tilted back and forth for 1 minute. Clumping of cells was positive.

Growth on Mannitol Salt Agar

Mannitol salt agar was prepared according to the manufacturers procedure. From another solid medium, a bit of growth was transferred onto the mannitol medium, the plates were incubated at 37°C for 24hrs. Presence of yellow colony growth in a positive test while no growth indicates negative test.

Triple Sugar Iron Test

With a sterilized needle a cultured material was obtained from a solid medium or a broth culture. The surface of the slant was streaked and the butt-stabbed 2 or 3 times. Cap was loosed and incubated at 37°C for 48hrs. Formation of hydrogen sulphide was determined by the blackening of the whole butt or a streak or ring of blackening at the slant junction. Glucose fermentation was indicated by the butt becoming yellow. If no other sugar is fermented, the slant would be red while the butt is yellow. This is referred to as an Alkaline/Acid or K/A reaction. If gas is also formed, it is indicated by the designation K/AG. If

lactose, sucrose or both have been fermented in addition to the glucose, then both the top and bottom of the slant would change to yellow indicating acid/acid or A/A reaction. If no sugar is fermented either at the butt or slant portions, the reaction is referred to as K/K.

Spore Staining Test

This was carried out according to the method [11]. The smear on the slide was flooded with strong carbol fuchsin and steamed. After 5mins the slide was washed with water. The slide was then decolourized with ethanol until all traces of red have been removed, and was washed thoroughly with water. The slide was then counter stained with Loeffler's methylene blue for 1-3mins. It was then washed and blot dry.

Heat Treatment Test

Bacterial suspension was made in a bijou bottles and were placed in water bath at 63°C for 30mins. The suspension were allowed to cool and inoculated in fresh nutrient media and incubated at 37°C for 24hrs. a positive test was indicated by growth. This indicates that the spores resist heat treatment.

Urease Test

Urease agar slant in a bijou bottle was inoculated and incubated for 24 to 48 hours at 37°C . The development of pink or red colour indicated a positive reaction.

Oxidase Test

A piece of filter paper wetted with a few drops of dilute solution (about 1%) of the oxidase reagent, tetramethyl-p-phenylene-diamine dihydrochloride. A bit of growth was obtained from a solid medium with a nichrome wire loop and was smeared on the wet piece of filter paper. The development of an intense purple colour by the bacterial cells in the smears within 30 seconds indicates a positive test. Failure of the development of an-intense purple colour within 30 seconds indicates a negative test.

Citrate Utilization Test

A simmons citrate agar slant in a bijou bottle was inoculated and incubated for 24 hours to 72 hours at 37°C . The development of a deep blue colour indicates a positive reaction.

Methyl Red-Voges-Proskauer (MR-VP)

5ml of MV-VP broth was inoculated and incubated for 48-72 hours at 37°C . The inoculated broth has been incubation for at least 48hrs. After this period of incubation, about 1ml of the broth was transferred to a small serological tube. To this small quantity 2-3 drops of methyl red was added, a red colour on the addition of the indicator signified a positive methyl red test. A yellow colour signified a negative test. To the rest of the broth in the originated tube, 5 drops of 40% potassium hydroxide (KOH) was added, followed by 15 drops of 5% α -Naphthol in ethanol. It was agitated and the cap was loosened and placed in a sloping position. The development of a red colour starting from the liquid-air interface within 1 hour indicates a VP positive test. No colour change occurs in a VP negative test.

RESULTS

The bacterial load of houseflies investigated has been determined. It shows that toilet areas have high range of bacterial load (2.2×10^6 - 3.9×10^8) that other sampling location, with 100% positive samples. This followed by rooms with 90% positive samples. The range, mean counts and percentage Positive samples of each location is presented in table 1. Medically important microorganisms were isolated from the external surfaces of house flies examined. Biochemical examination of the external body washes of house flies revealed that house flies are carriers of *S. aureus*, *S. saprophyticus*, *E. coli*, *Salmonella Species*, *Enterobacter aerogenes*, *Enterobacter agglomerans*, *Bacillus brevis proteus specie*, *Pseudomonas* and

Klebsiella species. The result of Biochemical analysis is presented in table 2

Table 1. The bacterial load of house flies in three housing locations (cfu/ml)

Sampling Location	Range of count	Means count	% positive
Toilet	$2.2 \times 10^6 - 3.9 \times 10^8$	3.05×10^7	100
Kitchen	$3.4 \times 10^3 - 8.2 \times 10^4$	5.17×10^4	80
Room	$2.6 \times 10^3 - 3.4 \times 10^5$	3.10×10^4	90

Table 2: Biochemical identification of bacteria isolates from body surfaces of House flies

S/N	Isolate Code	SP	S	M	H ₂ S	Gas	Glu	L	Cat.	U	C	IN	MR	VP	G/Rx	SH	Names of identified organisms
1.	Toilet A ₂	+	R̄	+	+	-	γ+	+	+	Slow	-	+	+	-	+ve long rod	-	<i>Bacillus alvie</i> ,
2.	Toilet A ₃	-	R̄	+	-	-	+	-	+	-	-	+	-	-	+ve long rod	-	<i>Bacillus spp.</i>
3.	Toilet B ₁	N/A	+	-	-	-	γ+	+	+	+	+	-	-	-	-ve short rod	-	<i>Klebsiella pneumonia</i>
4.	Toilet B ₂	+	-	+	+	+	γ+	+	+	+	+	-	+	+	+ve long rod	-	<i>Bacillus Spp:</i>
5.	Toilet C ₁	-	+ _R	-	+	-	γ+	-	-	+	-	+	+	-	+ve long rod	-	<i>Enterobacter spp.</i>
6.	Toilet C ₂	-	-	+	-	-	γ+	-	+	Slow	-	+	+	-	-ve long rod	-	<i>Pseudomonas cepacia</i>
7.	Toilet C ₃	N/A	+ _R	-	-	-	γ+	+	+	+	+	-	+	-	-ve short rod	-	<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i>
8.	Toilet A ₁	N/A	R̄	-	+	+	-	+	+	+	-	+	-	-	-ve cocci	-	<i>Pseudomonas cepacia</i>
9.	Toilet B ₃	N/A	R̄	+	-	-	R̄	-	+	-	-	+	-	+	-ve cocci	-	<i>Pseudomonas cepacia</i>
10.	Kitchen A ₃	N/A	+ _R	+	+	-	γ+	+	+	-	+	+	-	+	+ve cocci	-	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>
11.	Kitchen B ₁	N/A	R̄	+	-	-	γ+	+	+	+	+	-	+	+	-ve short rod	-	<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i>
12.	Kitchen B ₂	-	R̄	+	-	-	γ+	+	+	+	-	+	+	-	+ve long rod	-	<i>Proteus mirabilis</i>
13.	Kitchen B ₃	-	R̄	+	-	-	γ+	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	-ve long rod	-	<i>Pseudomonas pseudomallie</i>
14.	Kitchen B ₄	N/A	γ+	+	-	-	γ+	+	+	+	+	-	+	-	+ve cocci	-	<i>Salmonella spp:</i>
15.	Kitchen C ₁	N/A	R̄	+	-	-	γ+	-	+	Slow	-	-	+	-	+ve cocci	-	<i>Staphylococcus auricularis</i>
16.	Kitchen C ₂	N/A	+	+	-	+	γ+	+	+	+	+	+	-	+	-ve short rod	-	<i>Staphylococcus saprophyticus</i>
17.	Kitchen C ₃	N/A	+ _R	+	+	-	γ+	+	+	Slow	-	+	+	-	-ve cocci	+	<i>Staphylococcus intermedius</i>
18.	Kitchen A ₁	+	R̄	-	+	+	γ+	+	+	-	+	-	+	+	-ve long rod	-	<i>Pseudomonas pseudomallie</i>
19.	Room A ₁	N/A	+	+	-	-	γ+	+	+	+	+	+	-	+	+ve cocci	-	<i>Salmonella spp:</i>
20.	Room A ₂	-	R̄	+	-	-	γ+	-	+	Slow	-	+	+	-	-ve short rod	-	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>
21.	Room B ₁	N/A	+ _γ	+	-	+	γ+	+	-	-	-	+	+	+	-ve short rod	-	<i>Escherichia coli</i>
22.	Room B ₂	N/A	+ _R	+	+	+	γ+	+	+	+	+	-	+	-	-ve short rod	-	<i>Enterobacter spp.</i>
23.	Room C ₁	+	R̄	+	-	-	γ+	-	+	+	-	-	-	+	+ve long rod	+	<i>Bacillus licheniformis</i>
24.	Room C ₂	N/A	R̄	+	-	-	γ+	+	+	Slow	-	+	+	-	-ve short rod	-	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>
25.	Room C ₃	N/A	R̄	+	+	-	γ+	-	+	-	+	-	+	-	-ve short rod	+	<i>Proteus mirabilis</i>
26.	Room C ₄	N/A	R̄	-	+	+	γ+	+	+	+	+	-	-	+	-ve short rod	-	<i>Bacillus licheniformis</i>
27.	Room A ₃	-	R̄	+	-	-	γ+	-	+	Slow	-	+	+	-	-ve short rod	-	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>

Key: S = Sucrose, H₂S = Hydrogen sulphide, MR = Methyl red, SH = Starch hydrolysis, G/Rx = Gram reaction, L = Lactose, M = Motility, U = Urease, VP = Voges Proskauer, Cat. = Catalase, Glu = Glucose, G = Gas, C = Citrate, IN = Indole & SP Spores

Table 3: Frequency of occurrence of Bacteria isolates

S/No.	Isolates	Frequency	Percentage(%)
1	<i>Bacillus spp.</i>	14	17.9%

2	<i>Klebsiella</i> spp.	5	6.4%
3	<i>Enterobacter</i> spp.	9	11.5%
4	<i>Pseudomonas</i> spp.	8	10.3%
5	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	12	15.4%
6	<i>Escherichia</i> spp.	11	14.1%
7	<i>Proteus</i> spp.	3	3.8 %
8	<i>Salmonella</i> spp:	16	20.5%

The frequency of occurrence of various bacteria isolated from external body surfaces of house flies, shows that *Salmonella* spp. has the highest percentage of occurrence with 20.1%, followed by *Bacillus* spp. (17.9%). The least bacterial pathogens encountered were *Proteus* spp and *Klebsiella* spp., with 3.8% and 6.4% respectively. The result is presented in table 3.

DISCUSSION

Mechanical transmission of various pathogenic agents such as bacteria by housefly, *Musca domestica*, has been confirmed [1, 12]. Due to highly anthropophilic behaviour of this cosmopolitan species, wide variety of places investigated for fly pathogenic inoculations where the close relations with flies. The most important places for this issue are kitchen environments where the presence of food and garbage makes the shortest way for transmitting the pathogens. Isolation and identification of bacteria [13] from external surface of houseflies collected from kitchen premises in Nigeria has been done previously. This is the first report of bacterial infection of housefly in some homes within Sokoto metropolis. Hot and humid weather of this province prepare suitable conditions for housefly activities during the year.

Eight genera of bacteria which include *Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas* specie, *Bacillus* specie, *Enterobacter* species, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Salmonella* specie, *Proteus* specie, and *Klebsiella* species were isolated in this study, which also similar to previous researches [12, 13, 14] that reported the presence of *Bacillus* specie, and *Staphylococcus aureus* on the external body surface of the housefly. From their work, they also isolated *Micrococcus* specie, *Streptococcus* specie and *Acinetobacter* specie which were not found in this study. Kassiri *et al.*, [15] also isolated ten bacteria genera from their work similar to this finding [16]. The presence of *Escherichia coli* confirms faecal contamination and the presence of organisms of public health importance. A variety of bacterial diseases are transmitted by housefly which includes; typhoid fever, cholera, staphylococcal food poisoning (caused by *Staphylococcus aureus*) and Shigellosis caused by *Shigella* [17]. Their feeding and filthy habits make them efficient vectors and transmitters of human enteric pathogens. These implicate the flies as reservoirs of various human pathogens which confirm the incrimination of these flies in human diseases such as diarrhoea, typhoid and gastroenteritis [15].

CONCLUSION

We therefore conclude that flies are mechanical vectors in the spreading of diseases; the presence of the flies would indicate sanitary deficiency and unhygienic conditions in an environment. In order to prevent possible outbreak of infection, all possible breeding sites of flies should be eliminated and flies should be prevented from gaining access to contaminate human

food. Proper environmental sanitation should be implemented around any waste dumpsites to reduce breeding ground for flies. Furthermore, good hygiene practices such as covering of food, heating of left-over food before consumption and washing of kitchen utensils and laboratory equipment before use plus the use of insecticides will go a long way in reducing contact with these dangerous vectors. Fly control is still an important public health measure, which helps in eradicating these disease transmissions, especially in the developing countries.

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